

THERMAL FATIGUE OF UNIDIRECTIONAL GRAPHITE/EPOXY COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

Localized plastic flow in the epoxy near fiber/matrix interfaces causes interface cracking, altering the coefficient of thermal expansion (CTE) of two unidirectional graphite/epoxy materials that have been studied. The resulting CTE can be estimated by treating the segments of fibers circumferentially disbonded from the matrix as having been removed from the effective fiber volume. A difference observed in the rates of interface cracking in T300/934 and AS/3501-5A graphite/epoxy is correlated with the distribution in local fiber spacings, and also with the local plastic strain range in the epoxy. The interfacial plastic strains in the epoxy are much larger in the AS/3501-5A system, accelerating the damage rate.

INTRODUCTION

Local mechanical properties, such as of the resin near fiber/matrix interfaces, are often the dominant factor in determining the practical engineering properties of composites. The quality of the fiber/matrix interface, the degree of local plasticity and interface sliding, and the resulting microcracking distribution all affect material performance. Since the flow stress and strain hardening of materials in small volumes can differ radically from the bulk, it is actually the *in situ* mechanical properties that should be measured and studied. Recently, the determination of such quantities has become more practicable with the advent of techniques to measure displacements and strain fields over microscopic gauge lengths.

Examples of the new micromechanics include: 1) the determination of the coefficients of friction and depth of sliding of individual SiC fibers in a ceramic matrix by Marshall, using force-displacement measurements on individual fibers [1]; and 2) some recent work of our own in which the highly localized fatigue softening of the surface of an Al alloy was characterized by differential strains measured over various load sequences in individual grains [2,3].

Ultimately, a theory of the locally measured displacements is required to calculate local mechanical properties from experimental data. Before a model can be devised for a specific problem, the general deformation phenomenon and its sensitivity to the microstructure must first be defined. In this paper, we describe progress on the analysis of the microscopic phenomena which relate thermal fatigue damage to microcracking of fiber/matrix interfaces in graphite/epoxy (Gr/Ep) composites and the resulting change in coefficient of thermal expansion (CTE).

Gr/Ep composites are being considered for applications in space structures, where their dimensional stability under cyclic thermal loading in low Earth orbit (LEO) is important. Cross-ply laminates experience changes in their low initial CTE due to trans-ply cracking [4]. The expansion coefficient becomes more negative as cracking shifts the load to the 0° plies, as predicted by Bowles [5] using finite element analysis. The long-range stress, maximum at minimum temperature (since it results from differential expansion between the crossed plies), is the most important factor and usually produces damage in the first cool-down of a laminate. Delay of the first visible change in CTE to later in lifetime (more characteristic of a fatigue process) has not been found in short-term (< 1000 cycles) thermal cycling of cross-ply Gr/Ep, nor has any fatigue damage to unidirectional Gr/Ep been evident previously [6,7].

However, we recently discovered, by making high spatial resolution strain measurements, that large plastic strains were present at the fiber/matrix interfaces (Figure 1) of several unidirectional Gr/Ep composites for thermal cycles typical of LEO. We show here that this deformation ultimately leads to interface cracking and to CTE changes. We report the association of thermal fatigue-induced changes in the CTE of unidirectional AS/3501-5A and T300/934 Gr/Ep composites with fiber/matrix interface cracking. Rates of microcracking in the two composites increase with increased local fiber spacing and depend dramatically on the plastic strain amplitudes in the epoxy near the individual interfaces. Implications of these findings to analysis of Gr/Ep structural reliability and to the optimization of the local material properties for best resistance to thermal fatigue will be noted.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

Five centimeter long unidirectional bars of two Gr/Ep composites (AS/3501-5A, 15 plies; T300/934, 25 plies) were encapsulated in an argon environment and translated between hot and cold reservoirs by a pneumatic actuator at ≈ 5 min/cycle. CTE's were determined during fatigue by several optical techniques in which micrographs of samples were recorded at increments in sample temperature. For coeffi-

Fig. 1 Interfacial strains were measured in the epoxy between fibers for similarly spaced ($\approx 0.65 \mu\text{m}$) pairs of fibers in AS/3501-5A after 1 and 700 fatigue cycles. The strains were obtained from net displacements at room temperature for an intervening thermal heating to 138°C , and are compressive along a radius between the fiber centers on the first heating after specimen preparation.

coefficients larger than $3 \times 10^{-6} \text{ } ^\circ\text{C}^{-1}$, such as near specimen ends, it sufficed to find the displacements vs temperature directly from optical micrographs (500X) by stereoscopic analysis [8,9]. For the higher sensitivity needed in less damaged material, the micrographs were made of samples heated in an SEM. Changes in the longitudinal CTE (i.e., ΔCTE) given are relative to a 1 cm long (≈ 3 ply) strip of the unfatigued Gr/Ep composite placed on the fatigued specimen and coheated. The unfatigued Gr/Ep acted as a reference gauge [10] to compensate for magnification instability of the SEM. Data on the radial expansions of individual fibers bonded to the matrix were obtained using a thin reference gauge placed within the individual fibers on a surface cut normal to the fiber direction. In this case, the reference was a thin ($0.1 \mu\text{m}$) sheet of mica [10].

To characterize deformation in the epoxy near individual fibers, fatigue was interrupted after the specimen cooling phase. The specimen was sectioned normal to the fibers and the new surface was polished. Micrographs of interfacial areas taken at room temperature before and after the next heating cycle showed net displacements, resulting from substantial plastic flow (in excess of 5% strains) at the interfaces. Stereoscopic analysis of these images provided a strain sensitivity of $\approx \pm 5 \times 10^{-3}$ and the capacity to measure somewhat larger strains over gauge lengths as small as $0.1 \mu\text{m}$.

RESULTS

Microcracking at fiber/matrix interfaces, resulting from thermal fatigue, frees the large positive expansivity matrix to slide past the fibers as they contract slightly on heating. Near a specimen end, the expansion coefficient of a fatigue-damaged sample approaches that of the pure resin (Figure 2). The 500 μm distance over which these variations in CTE are visible in Figure 2 presumably approximates one-half the average spacing between places where the fiber and matrix remain bonded. This end effect is found everywhere fatigued unidirectional bars are cut, attesting to the ubiquity of the interfacial damage throughout the bar. Because of this end effect, the CTE of a fatigued bar measured by a linear displacement gauge depends on the bar length, and is largest when the bar is short and dominated by its ends. An analysis of results for AS/3501-5A shows that the specimen length must exceed 50 cm for 10% accuracy in CTE if the end effects are present. This untidiness we avoided by excluding the sample ends from the reference gauge measurement.

Fig. 2 Local CTE's measured over $\approx 50 \mu\text{m}$ gauge lengths and parallel to the fibers in AS/3501-5A as a function of distance from a surface cut normal to the fibers after fatigue cycles over the temperature range $-151/+138^\circ\text{C}$.

Fiber/matrix interface cracks are extremely difficult to identify directly from SEM micrographs, but are easily found by stereoscopy from displacement discontinuities of 20–200 \AA that the opened cracks present at the interfaces. Observations on a number of fibers in the two Gr/Ep composites reveal that portions of the circumference of each fiber/matrix interface are often microcracked by the first thermal cycle. The cracking occurs first at locations where the distance between neighboring fibers is largest. With continued fatigue the minimum fiber spacing (D_m) for which cracking is present decreases. The first complete separation of a fiber from the

matrix around its fiber circumference (in a plane normal to the fiber) requires that D_m equal the distance to the fiber's closest neighbor. In the AS/3501-5A of 65% volume fraction, all the fibers have at least one neighbor $0.5 \mu\text{m}$ and closer, and no change in CTE is seen until D_m falls to that value. Thereafter, ΔCTE is positive as local circumferential disbonding of fibers from the matrix allows the matrix expansion to increase. The measured distribution in nearest neighbor fiber spacings can be used to estimate the percentage of fibers which will be circumferentially disbanded as D_m falls (curve a, Figure 3). Bulk data on the CTE of a similar Gr/Ep vs fiber volume are available [11], and we find that the CTE of fatigue-damaged AS/3501-5A is accurately estimated from these bulk numbers if we treat the circumferential cracking as proportionately reducing the fiber volume fraction (Figure 3).

Fig. 3 The measured distribution in nearest neighbor fiber spacings (curve a) is used to estimate an effective fiber volume by considering all fiber sections circumferentially disbanded from the matrix as having left the volume. The resulting relationship of CTE to fiber volume fraction for fatigued AS/3501-5A (curve b) is within 20% of values for bulk Gr/Ep relating CTE to fiber volume fraction (curve c).

We are currently working on modeling the rate of interface cracking. One factor whose importance is immediately apparent from Figure 3 is the local fiber spacing, and recent data confirm the prediction that decreasing the local fiber separation postpones the onset of a change in CTE. Of equal importance is the local interfacial plastic strain amplitude, which turns out to be very dependent on the precise choice of fiber and matrix.

Data in Figure 4 show the rate of change in CTE is larger in a unidirectional AS/3501-5A than in a T300/934 Gr/Ep. The residual strains ($\bar{\epsilon}_r$) in Figure 4c are averages in the epoxy along a radius between fibers separated by $0.4\text{--}1.0 \mu\text{m}$, and are

Fig. 4 (a) Data for several temperature ranges show that a T300/934 material is less damaged by thermal fatigue than is AS/3501-5A. An important factor in this difference is apparent in (b) which shows that the radial expansion of the AS1 fiber is much larger than that of the average T300 fiber on the first heating after specimen fatigue and preparation. The result (c) is that the interfacial residual strains are much larger in the AS/3501-5A system.

derived from differential displacements found on micrographs taken at room temperature before and after heating to T_{\max} . Measurements of the radial expansions per °C of individual AS1 and T300 fibers bonded to the matrix (Figure 4b) reveal that both fiber types expand more in the radial direction than does the epoxy on the first heating after specimen preparation. The larger radial expansion of the AS1 fibers was associated with the larger interface strains (Fig. 4c) which are primarily plastic. Along with fiber spacing (slightly closer in the AS/3501-5A material), these strain amplitudes appear to be a principal factor in the difference in the rate of evolution of ΔCTE of the two Gr/Ep composites with fatigue apparent in Figure 4a. Local strain measurements show little variation in $\bar{\epsilon}_r$ with temperatures less than -80°C . So, in contradistinction to cross-plyed materials, it is the temperature range or perhaps even T_{\max} which is most critical to the fiber/matrix interface damage.

DISCUSSION

Both the local fiber spacings and the precise values of local mechanical and thermal properties of the Gr/Ep composites affect the resistance of unidirectional Gr/Ep to thermal fatigue. The major differences we find between the thermal fatigue damage to the unidirectional material and that previously reported [4,5] for cross-ply laminates are summarized in Table 1. Both types of damage will presumably be present in cross-ply laminates, with the fatigue-induced degradation of the fiber/matrix interfaces occurring later in lifetime. So, the strategy for any cross-ply Gr/Ep truss tubes for space applications will be to select by appropriate coatings a temperature range that strikes a balance between rates of damage in the two modes.

TABLE 1

Comparison of damage to unidirectional and cross-ply graphite/epoxy materials

	Cross-Ply	Unidirectional
Damaging Mechanism	Long-range stresses from differential ply expansion	Local plasticity from differential expansion of individual fibers and the epoxy
CTE	Negative as local loading shifts to 0° plies	Positive as matrix is freed to expand
Temperature Response	Damage most affected by low T_{\min} , which generates maximum long-range stress	Responds to ΔT or T_{\max} because damage is controlled by local plastic strain range

Clearly, in small volumes near the fiber interfaces the epoxy flows plastically even at room temperature, although the dry bulk resin is brittle below 200°C. Before we can calculate the local flow stresses and then exercise options to enhance fatigue resistance by selection of fiber/matrix combinations giving the least local damage, a model of the plastic deformation near the fiber/matrix interfaces is required. It is still unresolved why the observed radial expansion of the AS and T300 fibers is larger than the matrix expansion on the first measurement cycle. Treatment of the elastic-plastic aspects of the local strain as the local flow stress falls with increased temperature, changing the local stress state, and causing out-of-plane as well as in-plane distortions, is a crucial next step in this effort.

SUMMARY

An analysis of the mechanics of local deformation within a composite microstructure is computationally too complex without appropriate simplifications of the geometry. These choices must be guided by an understanding of the critical local phenomena, so that the salient events are incorporated into the model. We have examined the processes which affect the degradation in CTE of unidirectional Gr/Ep and note the following.

1. The graphite fibers are initially well bonded to the epoxy, but with fatigue interface cracks form - first at sites where the fibers are furthest apart. A local stress analysis is needed to determine if radial or shear stresses drive the separation and how the fiber boundaries and free surface affect the deformation and cracking processes.

2. Visible changes in CTE begin when sections of individual fibers become circumferentially debonded from the matrix. A theoretical analysis is needed to understand if the local plasticity at the sites where matrix and fibers remain bonded can alter the resulting CTE, and also to determine if local sliding of the matrix relative to the fibers (which might be modified by fiber roughness and plastic strain amplitude) is important to the expansion of the microcracked material.
3. A theory is needed to separate the effects of internal residual stress and surface relaxation on the measured surface strains. This is the key to deducing the local flow stress and strain hardening of the epoxy vs temperature near the fiber/matrix interfaces.

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REFERENCES

1. Marshall, D.B., An indentation method for measuring matrix-fiber frictional stresses in ceramic composites, 1984, 67, J. Am. Cer. Soc., 259-260.
2. Morris, W.L., Cox, B.N. and James, M.R., Microplastic surface deformation in Al 2219-T851, Acta Metall., in press.
3. Cox, B.N., Morris, W.L. and James, M.R., Two-stage microplastic surface deformation in Al 2219-T851, Acta Metall., in press.
4. Tompkins, S.S., Sykes, G.F. and Bowles, D.F., The thermal and mechanical stability of composite materials for space structures, IEE Space Tech. Conf., Anaheim, CA, 1985.
5. Bowles, D.E., Effect of thermal fatigue on the thermal expansion of composite laminates, J. Comp. Mat., 1984, 18, 173-187.
6. Babel, M.W., Shinate, T.P. and Thompson, D.F., Microcrack-resistant tubes for space applications, in Materials for Space - The Gathering Momentum, eds., J.T. Haggalf et al, SAMPE, 1986, pp. 429-439.
7. Johnson, R.R., Bluck, R.M., Holmes, A.M.C. and Kural, M.H., Development of space station strut design, 13th Int. SAMPE Symp., 1980, pp. 90-102.
8. Williams, D.R., Davidson, D.L. and Lankford, J., Fatigue crack tip plastic strains by stereomaging techniques, Expt. Mech., 1980, 20, 134-139.

9. Morris, W.L., James, M.R. and Zurek, A.K., The extent of crack tip plasticity for short fatigue cracks, Scripta Met., 1985, 19, 149-153.
10. Morris, W.L., James, M.R. and Inman, R.V., Measurement of fatigue-induced surface plasticity, J. Mat. Sci., 1982, 18, 1413-1419.
11. Yates, B., Overy, M.J., Sargent, J.P., McCalla, B.A., Kinston-Lee, D.M., Phillips, L.N. and Rogers, K.F., "The thermal expansion of carbon fiber-reinforced plastics," J. Mat. Sci., 1978, 13, 433-440.